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MINT^{grün} - Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory
Supporting and preparing students for their courses of study

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ABSTRACT

A survey from 2015, presented an analysis of the study situation and student's orientation success in Germany, has indicated a knowledge gap between schools' content of teaching and required engineering skills at the university. This paper presents an example on developing a new orientation program to bridge the gap of knowledge for the students with interests on fluid mechanics. The paper is divided into two main parts: The first one introduces the MINT^{grün} orientation program at the TU Berlin and gives the latest numbers and trends. The second part focuses on the development of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory of the department Fluid System Dynamic. A deeper insight on the structure and the teaching concept are given. This concept takes the mentioned survey into account.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: STEMgreen, Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory, TU Berlin, Thamsen

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INTRODUCTION

Since 2012, the Technische Universität Berlin offers a special orientation program in the subjects of mathematics, informatics, science and technologies (MINT^{grün}; English: STEM^{green2}). The department of Fluid System Dynamics at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering a laboratory dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering. The project laboratory provides useful engineering skills by teaching the students all the basics of using engineering software (such as Excel, SolidWorks, VBA) and guides them through advanced usage. It also imparts structured working methods while teaching the importance of sustainable engineering. Students achieve basic and advanced engineering skills (software and working methods) as well as exploring the multifaceted nature and the importance of sustainable engineering at the example of fluid machines. Since launching the project, it has been continuously evaluated by the students. The results show a very good rating for the teaching approach and a first analysis reveals that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program choose a STEM topic for their later studies.

1 BRIEF OVERVIEW OF MINT^{GRÜN} (ENGLISH: STEM^{GREEN})

1.1 Structure, numbers and trends

After graduating from high school, young people have to decide what they want to do professionally. Some choose to take an apprenticeship for about 3 years, whereas others choose an academic career and study at universities. The German universities offer a wide range of possible study courses. Most pupils feel overwhelmed by the countless possibilities and are unsure which course to take. They are expected to decide on “the right” study course which they will be practicing for the rest of their lives. This causes a lot of pressure and makes the decision even harder. Young people feel the need to be guided and orientated. Therefore, the Technische Universität Berlin launched an orientation program in 2012 called MINT^{grün} (English: STEM^{green}) to show graduated pupils the countless possibilities in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

The orientation program of STEM^{green} lasts two semesters and consists of different modules as shown in *Fig. 1*. The “Scientific Window” and the “Study Program Decision” are obligate courses, where students gain all necessary information on how to orientate themselves. The other modules are facultative and consist of basic lectures (i.e. engineering mathematics) and so-called Project Laboratories. Whilst lectures mostly use frontal teaching methods, the Project Laboratories focus on practical tasks and give the students the possibility to create a STEM-related object on their own. After taking the two-semester program, most of the courses can be transferred to the student’s chosen course of study.

Fig. 1: Structure of the orientation program MINT^{grün}

² STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics

1.2 Project Laboratories

One characteristic feature of the orientation program MINT^{grün} are the above-mentioned Project Laboratories which were specifically designed for STEM^{green} students. Especially in the earlier stages of a course of study, subjects are more theoretical. For a successful orientation, it is mandatory that students discover their practical and project related potentials. Therefore, the orientation program offers a wide variety of laboratories, which cover the fields of construction, chemistry, mechanics, physics, history, robotics, fluid mechanics and many more.

The department of Fluid System Dynamic at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering a laboratory dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE FLUID MECHANICS PROJECT LABORATORY

To introduce and explain the structure of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (FMPL) it is necessary to refer to a German survey from 2015 which analyses current study states and student's orientation success. The conclusions of this survey build the basis for the FMPL's structure. This survey [1, pp. 21-30] shows that students wish for a better support regarding the achievement of engineering skills (which were not taught in school) and handling of common engineering software such as MS Excel. A majority of the students mentioned a knowledge gap between the schools' content of teaching and required engineering skills at the university. Finally yet importantly, students criticise the lack of support for achieving scientific writing skills regarding their homework and their bachelor theses. The laboratory is designed to satisfy those needs.

Another significant part of STEM^{green} is a successful orientation of the students. Therefore, it shows them the importance of sustainable and responsible engineering, while exploring the diversity of STEM-related subjects. Consequently, current topics like "green energy" and "energy revolution" are discussed and an insight is provided. Students gain a deeper understanding of the fact that the "energy revolution" is not just generating electricity through renewable energy sources, but also improving the consumers (i.e. pumps³).

To show both sides to the students, the FMPL is divided into two parts, a lecture and a tutorial, as shown in *Fig. 2*. The next two subchapters provide a deeper insight on the lecture's and the tutorial's contents.

Fig. 2: Structure of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory

2.1 Lecture

A weekly lecture, held by the professor, gives the students theoretical concepts of fluid system dynamics and their general fields of application. The focus is put on driven machines (pumps) and their sustainable construction. Different types of impellers and their fields of application are explained. In addition, drinking water and

3 About 30% of Europe's electricity is used to power pumps. [2]

wastewater networks are presented and today's challenging phenomena are highlighted. The expansion of the students' knowledge in the field of fluid machines is encouraged by many examples with a practical orientation.

The discussed topics are complemented with a practical exercise, where students do measurements on fresh water pumps or a sewage pumps running in a fluid system.

The main goal of the lecture is to show the students the many possibilities on fluid mechanic related topics. It contributes mainly to the student's orientation.

2.2 Tutorial

The tutorial has a practical character and provides insight on how to do group projects in study courses. One Tutorial has space for 20 to 22 students and is accompanied by 1 research fellow and 1 research assistant. Two separate appointments are offered and therefore a total of 40 to 44 students are mentored. One of the main goals of the tutorial is to close the gaps mentioned in the survey [1] and prepare the students for their daily studying and engineering life. This includes the following topics and skills:

- Project management
- Group work and social competences
- Safe handling of calculation software (i.e. MS Excel)
- Safe handling of computer aided design software (CAD, i.e. SolidWorks)
- Measurements, sensors and characteristic curves
- Scientific writing (i.e. with MS word)
- Presenting project results (i.e. with MS PowerPoint)

To impart this knowledge, the rotor of a wind turbine model is designed within this tutorial. Many parameters (i.e. rotor diameter, blade number) are assigned by the group members. Therefore, every group owns their personal unique rotor. A rotor designed by the students is shown in *Fig. 3*. Consequently, the tutorial shows the producers side of sustainable engineering and renewable energy, whereas the lecture deals with the consumer's side.

(a) CAD model

(b) actual model

Fig. 3: Example of a rotor for a wind turbine model designed by the students

Fig. 4 summarises the FMPL tutorial's structure and which topics are discussed at a certain point.

Phase	Duration	Contents	Achieved skills
1	2 weeks	Organisation and project management	Organising group project Time management Creating project schedules with MS Excel
2	3 weeks	Fluid mechanics and wind energy	Basic calculations in MS Excel Handcrafting and testing airfoils Advanced usage of MS Excel (links, functions, variables) Complete rotor calculation
3	2 weeks	Computer aided design (CAD)	Introduction into 3D modeling Basic usage of CAD software Advanced usage of CAD tools (scripts & macros) Manufacturing of the student's rotor
4	3 weeks	Measurement techniques and test stands	Purpose of test stands Usage of sensors Measurement of each group's rotor Advanced usage of MS Excel (graphs, functions)
5	3 weeks	Writing and presenting skills	Creating templates for MS Word Basic usage of MS PowerPoint Scientific writing recommendations

Fig. 4: Structure of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory's tutorial

As shown in Fig. 4, the first two weeks are allocated to organisation and project management. In this phase students get support for their general study-related questions. Furthermore, working groups are assigned and basic project management skills are taught using MS Excel. This allows the students to acquire new skills and knowledge on teamwork and time management. Students are supported with useful tips and personal experiences to end their project successfully.

The following three weeks are spent on providing basic physical knowledge about fluid mechanics and wind energy. Simple calculations are first done in MS Excel to show the fundamental features of calculation software. It is followed by advanced usage of MS Excel, i.e. using links, functions and assigning variables. The main goal of those three weeks is to teach the students smart usage of engineering tools to make their life easier. Furthermore, students get a first idea on how airfoils work by crafting airfoils and testing them on a small wind tunnel. After this period, the first milestone is reached. Students have their personal rotor calculated with MS Excel.

The next two weeks are dedicated to the design of their calculated rotor with CAD software. At first, basics are taught to ensure the safe handling of the CAD software. Later, advanced skills are provided (i.e. scripts and macros) to speed up the students design process and teach smart usage of engineering tools. At the end of this phase, students have their personal rotor as a 3D model and it is ready for manufacturing. The second milestone is thus reached.

Three more weeks are allocated for describing measurement methods and test stands as well as for the actual measurement of the student's rotor model. Students gain a deeper understanding on sensors and how to acquire measurement data. Furthermore, data evaluation and visualisation using the MS Excel is also introduced.

The last three weeks are used to impart scientific writing and presentation skills. Under supervision, students design a template for scientific papers with MS Word,

which they can use throughout their study courses and even for their bachelor thesis. Practical exercises are used to achieve more detailed knowledge of using MS Word. A similar strategy is used to impart presentation skills. First, the basic usage of MS PowerPoint is taught and subsequently practical examples and personal experiences are given to the students.

3 RESULTS AND TEACHING APPROACH

Every student is unique. Every student uses different ways to learn and consequently it is mandatory to use different ways to teach. We attach great importance to address every learning type (auditory, visual, communicative, and motoric [3]) by the use of different media, such as exhibits, pictures/graphics, slides and presentations, experiments, group work and topic related examples. Since launching the project, it has been continuously evaluated by the students. The results show a very good rating for the teaching approach and good response for the concept (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Survey results regarding media usage

A first analysis reveals that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program choose a STEM topic for their later studies. Even people, who leave the university and start an apprenticeship, consider the contents of the FMPL as useful for their later jobs. The Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory as a whole was rated last semester with “very good” (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Student's summarised rating of the Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The teaching concept of this Fluid Dynamics Project Laboratory contributes highly to the orientation of our students. The lecture and the tutorial complement each other in a way that a huge field of fluid mechanical engineering is covered. Students gain a diversified insight on fluid mechanic related topics and their field of appliance. Due to the practical concept of the tutorial, students achieve various engineering skills and working methods, which can be used in many study courses or even in apprenticeships. Due to the teaching of basic and advanced skills regarding engineering software (MS Excel, MS Word, MS PowerPoint, SolidWorks), students are well prepared for their course of study. In this program, the students get supported in general studying related aspects as well as fluid mechanic related topics.

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